

Charging Ahead or Falling Behind? Equity in London's Electric Mobility Transition

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Summary

Despite a substantial increase in the overall number of public EV charging points, the spatial disparity of deployments continues to hinder the supply of infrastructure to meet the varied demand. This calls for a deeper understanding of socio-spatial inequality and models counting supply-demand balance for future planning. Our analysis takes London as a case study and investigates the changes in accessibility to public charging points between 2021 and 2024. We found that despite supply growth outpacing demand, accessibility in some areas has paradoxically declined. We applied global and local spatial regression models that incorporate demand factors to address the cause of inequality and concluded that tailored strategies at lower administrative levels are needed.

KEYWORDS: Transport; Electric Vehicles; Charging Infrastructure; Equity; Spatial Justice.

1. Introduction

The UK plans to ban new petrol and diesel vehicles by 2030 and require zero-emission cars by 2035, necessitating an expansion of public EV charging infrastructure from 35,000 to 300,000 chargepoints (Geospatial Commission, 2022). While this transformation is critical, policies increasing non-EV costs risk disproportionately burdening disadvantaged groups, such as council housing residents or self-employed van users, who face barriers to EV adoption.

Current supply-focused analyses, like Zhang et al. (2024), often overlook demand factors critical to equitable access. Strategic placement of chargepoints must consider both supply and who can access it (Peng et al., 2024), ensuring underserved communities are not left behind. Integrating demand-side analysis into planning can address socio-economic disparities and promote fair access to the green transition, aligning with inclusive policy goals to build a charging network that serves everyone.

By integrating demand analysis with supply-side evaluations, policymakers can identify areas where inequities persist and prioritise interventions that promote fair access for all communities, especially those most at risk of being left behind in the green transition (Dawkins et al., 2023). In essence, the question is not just about where the supply exists, but about ensuring that this supply is accessible to all, addressing both present and future needs in a manner that promotes equity and inclusivity.

2. Data & preliminary Analysis

Using the data summarised in **Table 1**, we analysed the trends in supply and demand for electric vehicle public charging infrastructure (EVCI) in London. First, we defined an accessibility metric by dividing

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the supply of public chargepoints by demand (represented by licensed EVs per zone), resulting in an accessibility score for each London Lower Super Output Area (LSOA) for 2021 and 2024. To evaluate changes over time, we calculated a difference variable by subtracting the 2021 accessibility score from the 2024 score. This metric allowed us to assess how accessibility has evolved spatially and temporally.

Figure 1.d illustrates that while the supply of public chargepoints in London has grown significantly, it has outpaced the increase in the number of licensed electric vehicles. However, **Figure 1.a** and **Figure 1.b** show how this infrastructure development is not spatially uniform and does not uniformly address the increase in demand.

To analyse the factors shaping these trends, we applied Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to identify statistically significant drivers of the identified accessibility difference between 2021 and 2024 at the global level and Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to uncover spatial variations, since - as shown in **Figure 1.c** - despite the faster increase of EVCI supply with respect to demand, several areas failed to translate into equitable accessibility gains. In fact, the Gini index for 2021 EVCI accessibility has a value of 0.813, while for 2024 it has a value of 0.579, indicating that inequalities have decreased, but still persist.

Table 1 Data and sources

Data	Description	Source
EVCI supply	N. of public EV chargepoint per LSOA	Department for Transport. National charge point registry.
EVCI demand	N. of EV licensed per LSOA	Department for Transport and Driver and Vehicle Licensing Agency. Vehicle licensing statistics data tables.
Approximated Social Grade (ASG)	N. of ASG individuals (in thousands) in different categories per LSOA. AB_C1: Higher and intermediate managerial/administrative/professional occupations (AB), and Supervisory, clerical, and junior managerial/administrative/professional occupations (C1) C2_DE: Skilled manual occupations (C2) and Semi-skilled and unskilled manual occupations; unemployed and lowest grade occupations (DE)	Office for National Statistics (ONS), NOMIS SG002EW, Approximated Social Grade. Census 2021.
Deprivation	N. of households (HH) (in thousands) deprived in 2 or more dimensions (D2+) per LSOA.	Office for National Statistics (ONS), Households by deprivation dimensions. Census 2021.
Car ownership	N. of households (in thousands) with 0 or 1 car (_0_1), or more than 2 vehicles (2+).	Office for National Statistics (ONS), Car or van availability. Census 2021.
House tenure	N. of households (in thousands) living in each different category: owned and rented.	Office for National Statistics (ONS), Tenure. Census 2021.
Accommodation type	N. of households (in thousands) living in: flats, terraced, detached & semidetached accommodations.	Office for National Statistics (ONS), Accommodation type. Census 2021. https://www.ons.gov.uk/data/sets/TS044/editions/2021/versions/4

Figure 1 a) Public EVCI accessibility score in 2021 - LSOA level. b) Public EVCI accessibility score in 2024 - LSOA level. c) Difference in public EVCI accessibility score between 2021 and 2024 - LSOA level. d) Number of licensed Electric Vehicles and public charging points in London from 2012 to 2024.

3. Results

The analysis of accessibility differences between 2021 and 2024 highlights several significant correlations (**Table 2**). Accessibility improvements negatively correlate with lower social grades, but are higher for highly deprived households (i.e., deprived in more than two dimensions). Median house prices are positively correlated with accessibility improvements, as well as population density, which shows a weak, yet positive, correlation with accessibility improvements, likely reflecting a greater reliance on public EVCI in high-density areas, where private parking and charging options are limited (He et al., 2022).

While OLS provides a citywide overview of trends without too many statistically significant variables at the global scale, the GWR analysis uncovers spatial disparities in EVCI accessibility and demand across different areas of London (see **Figure 2**). The spatial relationship between social grade and accessibility is more nuanced: accessibility improvements in 2024 correlate positively with higher social grades in East London, however, in South and Southwest London, lower grades (see **Table 1** for details on ASG categories) have a negative association with accessibility. These patterns reflect the complex spatial interplay between socioeconomic class and infrastructure improvements.

Table 2 OLS results.

Variable description	Variable name	Coefficient (std. dev.)
Approximate social grade, categories A, B, and C1	ASG_AB_C1	0.048 (0.030)
Approximate social grade, categories C2, D, and E	ASF_C2_DE	-0.135*** (0.023)
Accommodation type: detached and semi-detached	Acc_detached_se midetached	0.282 (0.248)
Accommodation type: flats	Acc_flat	0.313 (0.243)
Households deprived in 2 or more dimensions	D2+	0.271* (0.154)
House tenure: owned	HHT_owned	0.801 (1.411)
House tenure: rented	HHT_rented	0.994 (1.410)
Households with 0 or 1 car	HH_cars_0_1	-1.112 (1.422)
Households with 2 or more cars	HH_cars_2+	-1.670 (1.428)
Median house prices	Med_HP_2023	0.030*** (0.012)
Population density	Pop_density	0.003*** (0.001)

The dependent variable is the EVCI accessibility difference between 2021 and 2024. Standard errors are presented in parentheses.
 Estimation model: OLS.
 * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Accessibility improvements correlate positively with population density, particularly in Southwest London, underscoring the different role that urban cores play in driving EVCI improvements in different parts of the city. The opposite happens for median house prices, which positively correlate with accessibility improvements in South London, but not in central areas. House tenure and accommodation type also display distinct spatial patterns. Accessibility improvements positively correlate with both rented and owned properties in North London, yet this relationship is negative in Deptford. Accommodation types are statistically significant only in inner London, and do not present particular differences in terms of spatial variability, with positive correlations among accessibility improvements and all accommodation types.

Figure 2 GWR coefficients for different independent variables; the dependent variable is always EVCI difference between 2021 and 2024.

4. Conclusions

The combined OLS and GWR approach revealed inequities in EVCI distribution, identifying areas needing intervention for fairer deployment. The analysis highlights progress in addressing high-density and deprived areas but exposes persistent regional inequalities. Basing on these preliminary results - especially on the evidence provided by the GWR analysis - we recommend spatially targeted policies at the borough level – rather than at the metropolitan scale - to ensure more equitable access, since EVCI accessibility different parts of the city appear to be driven by different local factors. Scaling this analysis to other UK cities or nationally could uncover broader disparities and guide targeted policies for inclusive EVCI strategies, vital for achieving electrification goals. This is particularly relevant as the nation strives to meet ambitious electrification and sustainability goals, requiring scalable and

inclusive EVCI strategies that serve communities of all sizes and socioeconomic profiles.

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Biographies

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